

OSCAR

Open Science Clusters' Action
for Research & Society

CDIF-4-XAS

Implementation Plan

D3: Implementation plan and method for using XAS-CDIF

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Summary

This document describes the first proposal to integrate the IXAS — and IUCr — recommended formats for X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) data into workflows in the data processing and analysis platform *Galaxy* using the CDIF-4-XAS profile.

The [OSCARS project CDIF-4-XAS](#) aims to advance cross-domain interoperability of XAS data by implementing the [Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework \(CDIF\)](#) using the Data Description Initiative's Cross-Domain Integration (DDI-CDI) model.

The project has concluded the two first steps of its roadmap. Firstly, the [domain familiarisation step](#) helped to identify two major standards within the XAS community: [NeXus XAS \(NXxas\)](#) and the [XAS Data Interchange format \(XDI\)](#). The NXxas and XDI standards are the focus for harmonization of data description and formatting recommended by the [International X-ray Absorption Society \(IXAS\)](#) and the [International Union of Crystallography \(IUCr\)](#). Secondly, in the metadata modelling step, [both NXxas and XDI were mapped to CDIF](#) following the DDI-CDI recommendation where the main output was the definition of a variable cascade, that describes and harmonises both standards from the level of concepts and representation down to the level of instances.

This document focuses on the third phase of the roadmap: the development of implementation guidelines supported by working examples. We now turn to practical guidance for building interoperable, domain-agnostic solutions that enable FAIR data exchange.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning
CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CDIF-4-XAS	Describing X-Ray Spectroscopy Data for Cross-Domain Use Project
DDI-CDI	Data Description Initiative's Cross-Domain Integration
EXAFS	Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure
FAIR principles	FAIR Data Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
IUCr	International Union of Crystallography
IXAS	International X-ray Absorption Society
LCF	Linear Combination Fitting
NeX μ s NeXus	NeXus data format for N eutron, X -ray, and μ on science
NXxas	NeXus application definition (format) for raw data from an X-ray absorption spectroscopy
NXxasproc	NeXus application definition (format) for processed data from XAS
OSCARS	Open Science Cluster's Action for Research & Society Project
PSDI	Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure Project
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
XDI	XAFS Data Interchange format
XANES	X-ray absorption near edge structure
XAS	X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1. CDIF-4-XAS: Overview and roadmap

X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) comprises a set of widely used scientific methods with applications across Physics, Chemistry, Surface Science, Nanoscale Science, Biology, and Environmental and Earth Sciences.

The increasing number of XAS databases highlights the need for sharing and combining data produced by various research groups and facilities around the world. These databases can help minimize redundant experiments, suggest new research directions, and, more recently, support the development of machine learning models through shared training datasets. This approach promotes data interoperability, encourages reuse, and enhances the reproducibility of results.

However, reusing published XAS data remains time-consuming due to the variety of non-standard formats in which data is shared, often requiring tool modification to process and analyse it effectively. The XAS community would benefit from moving towards data standardisation. In our case, adopting standard formats for processing and analysis can serve as a showcase of the advantages of standardisation and offer a useful reference for broader efforts in this direction.

Roadmap

The OSCARS project CDIF-4-XAS aims to advance cross-domain interoperability of XAS data by implementing the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) using the Data Description Initiative's Cross-Domain Integration (DDI-CDI) model [1]. The main objective is to deliver a practical, domain-agnostic metadata model to enable FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data exchange across XAS research communities [2].

To achieve this, we adopted a streamlined application model focused on producing implementable tools and workflows that offer tangible benefits to researchers and data reusers. We are following a three-step roadmap:

1. Domain familiarisation: Identify and describe robust domain-specific and cross-domain XAS standards for data preservation, sharing, and semantic description.
2. Mapping to CDIF: The domain standards are mapped to CDIF using DDI-CDI to support data discovery, integration, and reuse.

3. Implementation Guidelines and Examples: Provide clear guidance and working examples to support the development of interoperable software tools that can process and analyse data in a platform-independent manner.

Currently, we have concluded the two first steps of this roadmap. Firstly, the domain familiarisation step [3] helped to identify two major standards within the XAS community: NeXus XAS (NXxas) and the XAS Data Interchange format (XDI). The NXxas [4] and XDI [5] standards are the focus for harmonization of data description and formatting recommended by the [International X-ray Absorption Society](#) (IXAS) and the [International Union of Crystallography](#) (IUCr). Secondly, in the metadata modelling step, both NXxas and XDI were mapped to CDIF following the DDI-CDI recommendation where the main output was the definition of a variable cascade, that describes and harmonises both standards from the level of concepts and representation down to the level of instances [6].

This document focuses on the third phase of our roadmap: the development of implementation guidelines supported by working examples. We now turn to practical guidance for building interoperable, domain-agnostic solutions that enable FAIR data exchange.

2. Current vs proposed use of XAS data

X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) is widely used across scientific disciplines, but the diversity of data formats—shaped by instrument configurations, software tools, database schemas, research goals, and publisher requirements—makes integration and reuse challenging. This fragmentation can be grouped into four categories: instrument-dependent, database-driven, software-dependent, and community-defined. Without standardization, accessing and combining XAS data for research, AI/ML training, or reproducibility often requires expert intervention. Establishing and promoting the use of common data standards is essential to improve interoperability and unlock the full potential of XAS analyses [3].

The Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI) project sponsored the development of XAS analysis tools for the workflow management platform Galaxy (see information box) to enable reproducible publishing of XAS data analyses [8]. These tools were developed and tested using published data, and used

to generate RO-Crates [9] for sharing results and enabling reproducibility. However, achieving broader interoperability still requires expert interpretation and manual data extraction. The XAS data value chain spans the full research lifecycle, from data acquisition to analysis and interpretation of results. While the XAS Galaxy tools support part of this lifecycle, further integration with other tools and analyses will require semantic annotations to complement RO-Crate metadata with domain-specific details—like materials, preparation,

Galaxy Tools and Workflows

Galaxy is a domain-agnostic workflow management system with over 500,000 users across disciplines like bioinformatics, chemistry, and environmental science. Deployed globally, it supports over 1 million jobs monthly (2023) [7]. Galaxy enables researchers to build, run, and share analytical tools and workflows without modifying core software. Tools are defined via XML wrappers and executed through a user-friendly interface. Workflows can chain tools, include logic-based steps, and be exported as RO-Crates for reproducible publishing.

and equipment—enhancing FAIRness, reproducibility, and replicability. In this section we describe how the CDIF-4-XAS profile can be used to provide those additional annotations.

XAS data is both an output and an input for processing and analysis tools. However, these tools require accepting a wide range of data formats, moreover the lack of accepted standards allows the appearance of various output formats which further complicate interoperability. This is due to the various types of software packages that are used for processing and analysing XAS data.

By comparing various published research papers performing XAS analysis, the overall analysis pipeline or workflow can be categorised based on what computational tools and processes are applied, and how the outputs of the workflow are used [8]. Figure 1 shows three broad categories of workflow which have been identified:

- Those comparing spectra in the Near Edge region qualitatively or visually (referred to as XANES in the diagram)
- Those comparing spectra quantitatively by fitting multiple known spectra to an unknown spectrum of interest in the near edge region (referred to as LCF in the diagram)
- Those that use Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS) measurements and fit scattering paths to the experimental results in this region (referred to as EXAFS in the diagram)

In addition to representing the overall workflow, the cylindrical nodes in the diagram show the variety of formats which can be found as supporting data for published research. This includes both intermediate formats and overall inputs/outputs to the workflow (shown in green). The selected formats for mapping in this project can be used for inputs and outputs of the XAS processing and analyses workflows. For this we propose the use of CDIF-4-XAS as the model for [re]defining these inputs and outputs for a new version of the XAS Galaxy tools [8].

XANES Workflow

LCF Workflow

EXAFS workflow

Figure 1 The XANES, LCF and EXAFS workflows supported by the XAS Galaxy tools. This image shows the variety of processing and analysis alternatives as well as the different formats which can be found as supporting data for published research, these can include text files, NeXus, XDI, Athena, Artemis and many others in combination. The data inputs and outputs highlighted in green are the data inputs which could be standardised to the ones described by CDIF-4-XAS

3. Expected outcomes of CDIF-4-XAS adoption

The implementation of standard formats for XAS analyses within the Galaxy platform, facilitated by CDIF-4-XAS, illustrates significant advantages for enhancing the functionality and interoperability of XAS processing tools, and supports their potential integration with complementary analytical systems. We anticipate that the adoption will:

- Reduce heterogeneity of input data
- Simplify identification of relevant data
- Streamline tracking of processing and analysis workflows
- Facilitate documentation of data publications (curation)
- Enhance interoperability.

The clearest advantage is the reduction in the number of input and output alternatives, consolidating them into a set of well-defined formats. Currently, adding support for additional XAS data formats to the Galaxy tools requires modifying the tools' source code, resulting in a lengthy turnaround between the identification of the format and the modification of the tools to facilitate its use. Having tools that accept standard formats can foster their adoption by the community.

The implementation of CDIF-4-XAS will improve traceability by clarifying which input data was used for each analysis step. Without it, reproducing results requires manually piecing together provenance information from publications to understand which data was used and how it was processed. At publication time, the enriched metadata provided by CDIF-4-XAS can be combined with RO-Crate provenance metadata to explicitly identify which data was used for producing a specific result, facilitating cataloguing and discovery.

Combining provenance and CDIF-4-XAS metadata can facilitate tracking of intermediate steps in data processing and analysis. Currently, this is challenging because the Galaxy XAS Tools produce non-standard file types [10] (e.g. Athena project files), which lack formal documentation required for publishing, interoperability and reusability. Relying on these non-standard formats creates dependencies that make provenance tracking difficult outside Galaxy. Generating standard data formats alongside provenance and CDIF-4-XAS metadata is expected to bridge this gap. This will support the use of alternative tools at each step, with the provenance metadata specifying the operations performed and those allowed after each processing/analysis step.

CDIF-4-XAS allows exposing key contextual information such as sample composition, target element and element edge. These metadata are highly valuable for facilitating discovery by domain users. This will facilitate publishing of data linked to research results, enhancing discovery (improving findability and accessibility).

The adoption of CDIF-4-XAS can also contribute to the reinforcement and long-term sustainability of the associated software tools. This could, for instance, enable the creation of a mapping tool that uses the CDIF-4-XAS profile to retrieve data, decoupling the data import process and eliminating the need to create custom import routines whenever new formats are introduced.

Finally, adopting CDIF-4-XAS can enhance interoperability by supporting the use of diverse tools across different stages of XAS data processing. CDIF-4-XAS enables interoperable integration of metadata, enriched with provenance metadata produced by the Galaxy platform and encapsulated within RO-Crates. This metadata allows both human users and software systems to trace data transformations and understand permitted operations. Moreover, it facilitates consistent integration of XAS data from heterogeneous sources — a frequent use case in the reuse of XAS data.

4. Technical details of the implementation

During the 2025 Dagstuhl Workshop “The Provenance Chain: Connecting and Reusing Data, Models, and Experiments” the CDIF-4-XAS and DDI-CDI working groups defined a set of five objectives to implement the CDIF-4-XAS profile in Galaxy and RO-Crates with the aim of supporting interoperability.

- Enhancing minimal data files with required metadata for CDIF
- Converting non-conformant formats to CDIF compliant formats (NeXus)
- Populating the CDIF profile from XDI (plaintext)
- Populating the CDIF profile from NeXus (hdf5)
- Extracting (meta)data from the original file using the populated CDIF profile

The existing Galaxy tools use Larch [11] as the underlying library for analysis functions, and will continue to do so as this is maintained by the wider XAS community. Similarly, wherever possible we will use existing libraries and/or community recommended processes for creating and interacting with the CDIF metadata. Some additional logic for interfacing the variables from the CDIF profile to the Larch functions will be needed and can be distributed as part of the Galaxy tools.

The following subsections explain in detail how these five objectives listed above are planned to be achieved in a technical implementation of CDIF-4-XAS in the Galaxy platform.

Enhancing minimal data files with required metadata for CDIF

In practice, many datafiles will only contain a minimal set of metadata, particularly lacking discovery metadata such as where the data was collected, when it was collected, and who collected it..

Some of this metadata will be required by the CDIF profile or to run later stages of the tooling.

Technical Requirements

1. Must allow researchers to input required metadata manually via a user interface (UI)
2. Must output data in XDI or NXxas file formats with additional metadata in the appropriate field(s)

3. Should have an extensible set of predefined profiles to minimise the amount of manual input required
4. Could support non-conformant formats
5. Could programmatically import information from an external archive

Proposal

The core requirements (requirements 1 and 2) are expected to be met by the solution proposed below in section 5.2. This decision reduces complexity in software development and simplifies the user experience. By design, this solution facilitates integration of non-conformant formats (requirement 4) and by the pre-definition of parsers it can resolve requirement 3. Requirement 5 could be integrated at a later point, e.g., as an extension to the tool, as an alternative or augmentation of providing additional metadata manually.

Converting non-conformant formats to CDIF compliant formats

In practice, many datafiles will not be in one of the recommended XAS formats (XDI, NeXus application definitions). The “.dat” extension (plaintext) and base .nxs (not following an application definition) are common in XAS data from typical X-ray experiments at large scale user facilities like the Diamond Light Source in the UK.

For reliable propagation of metadata to downstream tools, which may only accept standard formats, data should be converted to a CDIF compliant format at an early stage of analysis.

Technical Requirements

1. Must be possible to convert from at least one de facto plaintext standard (e.g., Diamond B18 transmission .dat) to at least one CDIF compliant format (e.g., XDI).
2. Must be possible to convert from at least one de facto HDF5 standard (e.g., Diamond B18 transmission .nxs) to at least one CDIF compliant format (e.g., NXxas).
3. Should be possible to convert to either XDI or a NeXus application definition (e.g., NXxas).
4. Could be possible to convert to any of the relevant application definitions (NXxas, NXxasproc, NXxas_new).
5. Could be possible to convert from multiple plaintext/HDF5 formats.
6. Must be possible to extend the tool with other formats which are not initially supported.
7. Must be able to populate the output file with the contents of the input file without manual input.

8. Could be possible to include additional user provided information to augment or correct metadata for the final output.

Proposal

A promising building block identified for resolving most of the above requirements is the [NeXusCreator](#) project [12, 13], developed by Hector Perez Ponce (HZB) under the permissive Apache 2.0 license . The project is written in Python, and has both Python bindings when imported as a library and a command line interface (CLI) executable. It is not currently versioned or published (e.g. via PyPi or Conda). The project includes [parsers](#) for different (non-conformant) data formats¹, which is designed to be extensible. When given an example file, a custom YAML “NeXus definition” .nxd file is automatically generated. This can then be inspected and manually modified to correct any errors. Based on this semiautomated definition file, NeXusCreator can be used to convert files from the original data format to NeXus format.

Minimum Viable Product

- A. Using a representative example file for Diamond B18 .dat files, generate and curate a .nxd file.
- B. Using a representative example file for Diamond B18 .nxs files, generate and curate a .nxd file².
- C. Create a Dockerfile for the NeXusCreator including the above .nxd files as static files required for the transformation(allowing distribution, versioning, reproducibility).
- D. Publish Docker image on STFC harbor and register with PSDI container registry.
- E. Create a Galaxy tool wrapping the Docker image
 - a. Accepts plaintext or hdf5 files
 - b. User must specify input format from dropdown/radio select
 - c. For any metadata required but not included in the input file, first attempt to programmatically determine this from the format (e.g., metadata about the facility and beamline at which XAS data was recorded will be implicit)
 - d. User optionally provides additional metadata not covered by the input file or the programmatic extraction via form based input
 - e. Tool formats all input arguments and calls NeXusCreator
 - f. Output is a conformant NXxas file.

This minimal viable product is expected to meet requirements 1, 2, and 5 (since some parsers are already defined), as well as requirements 6, 7, and 8. In contrast, it is not expected to meet requirements 3, 4, and 5 (since one could always define more parsers).

¹ <https://nexuscreator.readthedocs.io/en/latest/plugins.html#built-in-plugins>

² Nexus description (.nxd) files define the structure that NeXusCreator uses when generating NeXus files.

Further developments

Output in XDI format (requirement 3)

- By design, the NeXusCreator can be used to convert XAS data to the NeXus specification based on the HDF5 file format.
- For XAS data, XDI will be a CDIF compliant format and may be preferred due to being plaintext and therefore more compatible with downstream tooling.
- NeXusCreator, via the Python bindings, instantiates an object containing all data loaded via the parser. Therefore, one could (rather than using the existing functionality to inject this to a NeXus file) write it to a plaintext file under the appropriate keys/columns via custom scripting and update the Galaxy tool interface to integrate this as an output option.

Output in other NeXus formats (requirement 4)

- Generate additional .nxd files and include these in future releases of the Docker image.
- Update the Galaxy UI xml to accept these as output options.

Support additional input formats (requirement 5)

- As required, define new parsers (following existing patterns) and update image and tool xml accordingly.

Populating the CDIF profile from XDI (plaintext)

The core purpose of the project is to create CDIF metadata which describes XAS spectra. XDI specifically is a plaintext format, with a “header” consisting of *key: value* mappings and a tab-separated body containing the numerical data itself. The XDI format is [publicly specified](#) [5]. Practically speaking, XDI, as a plaintext format, is better supported by most existing tooling.

Technical Requirements

1. Must accept conformant XDI files with all required fields populated.
2. Could accept non-conformant plaintext formats directly.
3. Must output the populated JSON-LD profile for the input spectrum.
4. Should not depend on an external service in order to not prohibitively increase maintenance requirements.

Proposal

Harvard Dataverse is a repository service used by the wider CDIF community [14]. In addition to hosting the data, it supports additional plugin tools which can act on

datafiles/sets stored there. Prototype implementations for metadata extraction, export of CDIF profiles, and accessing “data points” contained in the file have been demonstrated. In this prototype, the API developed fetches data hosted in Dataverse, but this is not a strong couple and the core business logic is intended to be “stand alone” and could be applied to data sourced from elsewhere. Furthermore, both the core Dataverse service and the additional tooling is containerised with Docker, and so could be leveraged for this use case without requiring the overhead of running a new service whilst also beginning to adopt and interface with best practice from elsewhere in the community in software and tooling as well as metadata profiles.

Minimum Viable Product

- A. Create a Dockerfile layering, the core Dataverse, [CDIF export service](#) images into a single image along with the scripting currently used in the [Larch Extract Group tool](#).
- B. Ensure that the [resource files](#) required for the export service are up to date for XDI (including SHACL rules).
- C. Publish Docker image on STFC harbor and register with PSDI container registry.
- D. Update the Larch Extract Group tool:
 - a. Replace conda dependencies with explicit image dependency.
 - b. Accepts conformant XDI files.
 - c. Optional “populate CDIF” boolean in the UI.
 - i. File uploaded to containerised Dataverse.
 - ii. Request sent to metadata service to extract CDIF profile from the datafile.
 - iii. Request sent to metadata service to get the full profile including datapoints.
 - iv. SHACL validation applied using the [pySHACL](#) library.
 - v. Parse response for relevant variables.
 - vi. Pass relevant variables to existing Larch functions (starting with pre-edge).
 - vii. Write CDIF to file as JSON-LD and output file from the tool.

This minimal viable product is expected to meet requirements 1, 3, and 4, but it is not expected to meet requirement 2.

In practice, it will be more practical to do conversion to XDI in the former NeXus Creator based tool, which will explicitly address converting non-conformant formats.

Populating the CDIF profile from NeXus (hdf5)

The core purpose of the project is to adopt CDIF to describe XAS spectra in a way that is interoperable across domains. NeXus specifically encompasses several “application definitions”, including NXxas, NXxasproc and NXxas_new. While strictly speaking NeXus only

defines a specification, in practice files saved as NeXus (.nxs) use the binary Hierarchical Data Format HDF5. This saves the data with a hierarchical structure, and supports symbolic linking within and between files. Practically speaking, NeXus presents a greater challenge than plaintext formats as it is less intuitive and needs to be read and browsed using appropriate libraries.

Technical Requirements

- a) Must accept at least one conformant NeXus format (e.g. NXxas) files with all required fields populated.
- b) Should accept all conformant NeXus formats (NXxas, NXxasproc, NXxas_new).
- c) Could accept non-conformant HDF5 formats directly.
- d) Must output the populated JSON-LD profile for the input spectrum.
- e) Should not depend on an external service in order to not prohibitively increase maintenance requirements.

Proposal

Generally speaking, the approach taken for XDI files should be followed. However, additional consideration is needed to account for the binary format of NeXus/HDF5. In the first instance, the most practical approach will be to use the Python bindings of the NeXusCreator tool to also output XDI. This can then be passed natively to the existing pipeline as described above without any further development being required here.

Further developments

Ideally, it would be possible to keep files in a NeXus format without requiring their conversion to XDI. Both formats are recognised by the domain community, and with the continuing development of NXxas_new there is a risk of not being able to fully leverage the benefits of it if we fully commit to only supporting XDI (e.g. XDI files are explicitly single spectrum, whereas NeXus offers the possibility of multispectra support). As a result, further development could extend the Dataverse metadata extraction service with an hdf5 reader, so that NeXus (and other formats in principle) could be loaded directly.

- 1) Extend Dataverse metadata extraction service with hdf5 reader/parser
- 2) Ensure that the [resource files](#) required for the export service are up to date for NeXus.
- 3) Release a new version of images/tool interface:
 - a) Accept NeXus (HDF5) files directly.

Extracting (meta)data from the original file using the populated CDIF profile

In order to provide value to researchers, it must be possible to use the populated CDIF profile to interact with the data as part of an analysis workflow. At a basic level, it must be possible to extract the independent (e.g., photon energy) and dependent (e.g., absorption coefficient) variables from the data, which are used for the further analysis. It should also be possible to leverage the profile to do something which cannot be done by the existing analysis tools, to demonstrate the benefit of having this additional metadata and using the recommended file formats (XDI, NeXus).

Technical Requirements

- 1) Must be possible to extract the independent variable (energy) without requiring the user to provide the specific path or column key in the underlying file.
- 2) Must be possible to extract the dependent variable (μ or equivalent) without requiring the user to provide the specific path or column key in the underlying file.
- 3) Must provide extracted variables to following analysis steps without further user intervention.
 - a) For NXxas (and NXxas_new), the dependent variable(s) of interest will be stored as two arrays: [absorbed beam](#) (i.e. transmitted/fluorescence intensity I_t/I_f) and [incoming beam](#) (incoming intensity I_0). This needs to be converted to the absorption co-efficient using a different formula for either transmission or fluorescence before normalisation (the first stage in analysis).
- 4) Should be possible to provide a flat list of spectra and a criteria to group by, and output averaged spectra corresponding to each distinct group.
- 5) Should automatically extract and provide optional arguments where they exist, such as edge energy.
- 6) Could leverage other metadata from CDIF to provide future functionality that improves the user experience.

Proposal

Rather than having a standalone tool which purely reads variables from the profile, it will be more efficient to access this information while it is in memory. As noted above, this can be achieved with a request for the datapoints to the Dataverse service.

Once “column” (dependent/independent variables) fields are loaded into memory, these then need to be passed to analysis software, starting with normalisation. The required arguments to [Larch’s pre-edge function](#) are *energy* and *mu* (the [absorption co-efficient](#)). In some cases energy values are not included, but need to be calculated from other data such

as the monochromator angle. Similarly, μ is often not included in the raw data (as this is not directly measured) but is rather calculated from a set of measured intensities.

Additionally, we will have metadata beyond the minimum column variables, and should use this. Given a list of spectra we can group them by:

- Element
- Edge
- Sample conditions

And average or merge these spectra before preceding to normalisation. In terms of development required, note that since the functionality will be implemented in the same tool that generates the profile, some of the points below will be the same as in the previous sections (5.3, 5.4).

Minimum Viable Product

- A. Create a Dockerfile layering, the core Dataverse, [CDIF export service](#) images into a single image along with the scripting currently used in the [Larch Extract Group tool](#).
- B. Ensure that the [resource files](#) required for the export service are up to date for XDI (including SHACL rules).
- C. Publish Docker image on STFC harbor and register with PSDI container registry.
- D. Update the Larch Extract Group tool:
 - a. Replace conda dependencies with explicit image dependency.
 - b. Accepts conformant XDI files.
 - c. Element to select column variables for import has options corresponding to the DDI-CDI concept variables, but if none are provided then defaults to checking these variable names to automatically select appropriate columns.

This minimal viable product is expected to meet requirements 1, 2, and 3, but it is not expected to meet requirements 4, 5 and 6.

Further developments

To meet requirements 4, 5 and 6, additional options in the UI would be added using the same principle: the user can select one or more names of DDI-CDI concept variables, and they are used to group the data before averaging grouped spectra. If optional values for E0 are not provided, but present in the metadata, we can automatically query the profile for the appropriate variable as well.

5. Workflow-level metadata

Enhancing history/workflow-level metadata

Currently, data analysis steps performed by users of the Galaxy platform are recorded as a *history*. It is also possible to either extract retroactively, or define proactively, a *workflow* which defines the individual stages of the analysis performed. Either or both (as a “workflow invocation”) of these can be exported from Galaxy as an RO-Crate. These represent the overall body of work that a researcher has carried out, and would correspond to the data object which supports a publication of their research. As a result, it should contain metadata to describe the overall process as well as discovery metadata.

Currently, the RO-Crate metadata is not linked to CDIF, and the files contained in the export are primarily Galaxy specific. Ideally, they should follow best practice and contain as much metadata as is available.

Requirements

1. Must accept Galaxy exports (Datasets History, Workflow Invocation, Workflow files) as input.
2. Must output either an RO-Crate metadata file (JSON) or a CDIF profile (JSON-LD) which describes the contents at a “manifest” level
3. Should include “discovery” level metadata such as dates, authors etc.
4. Should include scientific “discovery” level metadata such as the element(s) of interest, physical properties varied in the experiment, technique applied etc.
5. Could include provenance and associated context metadata from the analysis stages such as which raw inputs were averaged together, identifiers for the analysis software used, etc.
6. Could include provenance and associated context metadata from upstream processes such as sample preparation.

Proposal

As a proof of concept, export of RO-Crates from Dataverse has been demonstrated. A Dataverse dataset can include multiple files, and so this could include the underlying datafiles, their populated CDIF profiles, and representations of the workflow. All of this information would therefore be available for metadata extraction.

Currently, only “*manifest*” level information is extracted to point to the constituent files (as well as required metadata for the Dataverse dataset. Adding richer metadata is, in principle, possible but is out of scope for the development capacities available. It is expected that

other projects involving the core RO-Crate developers at Manchester will add functionality in this area.

In terms of this project, the use of Dataverse for the above tools will build experience with adopting this technology. As more features are developed by the wider CDIF/RO-Crate community, we can then leverage these by creating equivalent tools which, rather than submitting and extracting metadata for a single XAS spectrum, act on the entire body of work carried out by a researcher.

Publishing history/workflow-level metadata on PSDI Invenio

The final stage in a researcher's process should be to publish their data (object) in a repository. This will contain all data from analysis, but should also expose metadata about the overall research process which makes their research/data findable. As well as "administrative" metadata (e.g. who, when) it should also include technical or scientific information which may be useful to future use cases, such as what techniques were employed, sample details, conditions varied etc. Finally, provenance information (either just for analysis or including information from "outside" the analysis platform) could be included at this level.

Requirements

1. Must be possible for a user to submit (push or pull) an (uplifted) RO-Crate to PSDI Invenio instance.
2. Should not require the user to manually input information recorded in JSON format(s), but instead programmatically extract metadata from the input object.
3. Must allow the user to provide additional metadata for their publication to account for anything that cannot be extracted from the RO-Crate metadata.
4. Should not depend on an external service (other than the existing Galaxy and Invenio) in order to not prohibitively increase maintenance requirements.

Proposal

InvenioRDM has a [REST API](#), which accepts requests to create and modify draft publications for users who have generated an API key. Furthermore, it can be [configured](#) with custom, domain specific metadata. Currently PSDI has this for the BioSim and Data to Knowledge partner projects. The fields defined here are then searchable criteria.

On the Galaxy side, there are already methods to [connect to InvenioRDM instances](#). For our use case we may need to extend this to extract the domain specific metadata.

One challenge will be sourcing sufficient metadata. Even if metadata can be programmatically extracted from existing sources, this does not help if that metadata was not originally captured, and it is unlikely that there is any natural way of populating “bibliographic” style metadata such as related identifiers, or contributors other than the user providing the API key.

Minimum Viable Product

- 1) Define domain specific metadata corresponding to high value discovery metadata from the CDIF for XAS profile, and any other information from the RO-Crate or equivalent level (e.g., CDIF prov).
- 2) Update STFC maintained Galaxy instance to a version which supports the Invenio export (minimum version 25.0).
- 3) Develop a Python script which:
 - a) Reads from JSON
 - b) Accepts InvenioRDM API key
 - c) Submits request to update metadata via the InvenioRDM API
- 4) Create Dockerfile for the above script.
- 5) Publish Docker image on STFC harbor and register with PSDI container registry.
- 6) Create Galaxy tool UI which:
 - a) Accepts user’s InvenioRDM API key
 - b) Accepts multiple CDIF JSON-LD files as input
 - c) Calls above script

This minimum viable product is expected to meet requirements 1, 2, and 4.

Requirement 3 is expected to be trivially solved by only creating/updating the publication in the draft state, meaning the user can edit it with the existing InvenioRDM UI as usual and with the functionality that offers.

6. Future developments

Although creating another Galaxy tool is a convenient way to edit publication metadata contained in JSON files in a user's history, it would be ideal to extend the existing Invenio integration in Galaxy to support this metadata extraction and upload process.

For this reason, the above script should be written in Python as the Galaxy server core code is also written in Python which would lower the barrier to migrating this at a later date.

In the medium term, the Galaxy server code could be forked and this local copy deployed. This would be an intermediate step towards the long-term goal of merging changes upstream. It would provide greater control and scope for embedding use-case-specific logic, which, while not ideal, would facilitate faster development. It would also remove reliance on the core community's approval and release process.

This initial plan is a proposal for implementation. The final result may be either a single tool that implements all the operations or a set of tools that implement each operation independently. We will continue to refine and adapt the implementation plan as needed during the development phase. Ultimately, this will document the design and development process and inform the final report on the implementation.

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